

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING-LEARNING ENGLISH IDIOMS

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Abstract

The English language has become an integral part of our daily lives, hereby making it necessary to teach and learn the language in order to communicate with those who speak other languages. Since idioms are an essential component of the English language, they play a crucial role in teaching and learning it. But, the process of teaching and learning English idioms has always been a challenging one and requires a lot of experience and creativity, since they are not always easy to understand, remember and use. This study aims to investigate the perspective of English teachers on idioms in language teaching and learning. It assumes that awareness of the role of knowing English idioms will be of great use. During this very study we used the meta-synthesis method to find some common results and to identify overall trends whereas teaching-learning English idioms. So, we've come to the conclusion that a systematic review of the significance of teaching-learning the idioms is really beneficial.

Keywords: awareness, communicative skills, cultural applicability, idiomatic, language proficiency.

1. Introduction

Language is more than just a collection of words; it also includes the diverse range of idiomatic expressions, cultural references, and subtleties that give it its truly distinctive character. Particularly, idioms are essential for comprehending and communicating clearly in any language. [1] This article aims to investigate the importance of teaching and learning English idioms, emphasizing their cultural applicability, communication improvement, and overall language proficiency. [2] Idioms are a crucial component of spoken language in daily life. Making effective use of idioms shows that one is a fluent and natural speaker of the language. [3] When you use idioms in your speech or writing, you can sound more like a native speaker and express your ideas clearly and concisely. After conducting a systematic review of numerous studies and performing a meta-synthesis of numerous works on English idioms, we can say with certainty that these expressions are frequently used in spoken English and play a significant role in language learning. Additionally, we may say that these expressions are complicated and challenging to comprehend, remember, and use, but knowing and using them can surely benefit a lot. [4]

2. Materials and Methods

During the study there were consulted numerous books, dictionaries, and articles on this topic. In this very study the systemic review of multiple theories of idioms was tried. By combining different studies and ideas of idiom structure and meaning, we have aimed to come up with some new useful results in order to clarify the importance of teaching-learning the English idioms. In fact, after all particular attention was paid to the meta-synthesis method of research, that is the basic tool of the work. Thereby, after a long qualitative study, we have managed to combine all our findings and then, to make known the data of multiple studies to summarize common results and to point out overall trends.

3. Defining the Term of Idiom

Many linguists claim that it is practically impossible to create a general definition of idiom that would cover all its characteristics and functions. The word "Idiom" is of Greek origin and means "standing apart on its own". An idiom, then, is a construction which stands apart from the rest of the language on account of this irregularity and examination would show that they are almost all of a popular rather than a literary character, belonging to the spoken rather than the written language. Idioms are considered figures of speech, which are defined as "a group of words in a fixed order, that have a particular meaning that is different from the meanings of each word on its own." [4]. In the Longman Idioms Dictionary (1998) the idioms are defined as "a sequence of words which has a different meaning as a group from the meaning it would have if you understand each word separately" [3]. The Dictionary of English Colloquial Idioms writes that "idioms are phrases which allow no elements to be replaced by a synonym" [4].

4. Results

4.1 Cultural Importance

The history and culture of countries that speak English have a significant impact on English idioms. They are able to reflect entirely the way of being and thinking of a nation. So, idioms must not be broken up into their elements, as they are referred to as a fixed expression and should be learned as a whole [5]. Students gain understanding of the beliefs, practices, and traditions of the people who use idiomatic expressions by learning them. For instance, expressions like "raining cats and dogs" or "a piece of cake" may not make sense when taken literally, but they reveal the rich cultural heritage and creativity that are rooted in the English language. [6] Brenner believes that native English speakers simply use idioms without being aware what constitutes them. [7] Meanwhile a foreign student should work a lot on their learning. Although, idiom

acquisition gives students the opportunity to understand cultural nuances, deepening their appreciation for and comprehension of the English-speaking world. Idioms are deeply ingrained in a language's culture and history. The customs, traditions, and values of English-speaking societies are better understood by mastery the idioms that are used in conversation. The overall language ability will improve as a result of the increased cultural awareness, and one will be able to interact with native speakers more effectively. [2]

4.2 Communication Improvement.

Idioms can enhance the impact, color, and depth of your communication. They are able to concisely express difficult concepts or feelings. You can make your writing or speech more persuasive, memorable, and engaging by incorporating idioms into it. You can engage in conversations more actively and appreciate the diversity of the English language by using idioms to help you understand subtle distinctions, humor, and sarcasm. [3] Idioms give language an additional layer of expressiveness and flair, allowing speakers to succinctly communicate complex ideas or emotions. Learners can improve their communication skills and participate in more meaningful conversations by adding idiomatic expressions to their vocabulary. Idioms frequently have connotations and metaphorical meanings that are challenging to translate literally. [8, p.239] In the same time, they can help with effective communication, comprehension, and thus helping students become more confident and fluent speakers of English by helping them understand and use them appropriately. Because they frequently don't have literal meanings, English idioms can be difficult for non-native speakers to understand. Irujo points out that idioms are commonly used in television or books, it means learners get in touch with them in non-interactive situations and consequently, they don't have the possibility to ask what these expressions mean or get any feedback on their own usage [9, p.237]. Consequently, it's important to be familiar with the figurative or metaphorical meanings of idioms in order to understand them. Because idiomatic expressions are used in a variety of contexts, such as literature, movies, and casual conversations, learning idioms will improve the ability to understand and interpret them. Moreover, knowing how to use them properly can help you establish rapport with native English speakers as by encouraging connections and understanding between people, it demonstrates your readiness to interact with their language and culture.

4.3 Language Skills.

Fluency and general language proficiency are increased by idiom mastery. Irujo points out that the learning of idioms is essential for vocabulary practice of a second language [9, p.240]. As idioms are widely used in books, films, television shows, and other forms of media, make them a fundamental component of the English language. It's essential for proficient English speakers to be able to identify and decipher idiomatic expressions in everyday situations. Idiom learning provides students with the knowledge and skills they need to successfully negotiate the nuances of the language, improving their ability to communicate with native

speakers. On the other hand, due to the fact that idioms are frequently used in different forms of English media, it also helps students improve their reading and listening comprehension. As well, they increase vocabulary. Idioms frequently use uncommon words that aren't typically found in language textbooks, as a result, idiom study exposes a student to various linguistic nuances and broadens the vocabulary. [5, pp.125-130] Idioms captivate and fascinate English language learners, but they are frequently reluctant to use them because figurative language is a tricky aspect of the language. To introduce idioms to a second language learner, however, appropriate teaching-learning strategies and methods should be used, enabling them to overcome their idiom phobia and continue to pick up idioms outside of the classroom. In general, learning idioms requires sophisticated linguistic and cognitive abilities, which go beyond merely memorizing catchy phrases or words. But, still, learning and using English idioms is a certain way to improve the language skills.

4.4 Cognitive Benefits.

Beyond language acquisition, learning idioms has cognitive advantages. It forces students to use original thought, interpret figurative language, and draw connections between words and their definitions. [10] Students improve their critical thinking, linguistic flexibility, and problem-solving skills by interacting with idiomatic expressions. Cognitive flexibility and a deeper understanding of language as a whole are fostered by the mental operations required to understand and use idioms. In addition, the memory strategies used to acquire idiomatic language, develop the cognitive skills of a learner. These memory strategies can assist students in recalling a large amount of idioms. The keyword, storytelling, and semantic organization are all well-known mnemonics that are commonly used whilst learning-teaching a foreign language and, additionally, facilitate learning and encourage mental development. [8] Thus, all these conduct to the improvement and growth of the cognitive skills. Even Levorato claims that the reason why idioms are so amazing is that they engage imagination, can transform abstract meaning into concrete ones and enrich the meaning of simple concepts. [11]

5. Conclusion

The idiom is practical and is one of linguistics' figurative speeches. People from one area or nation frequently use it for both informal and formal spoken and written purposes. Idioms are a crucial component of universal communication in addition to being a part of language. We use idioms for theoretical purposes, and if we classify idioms, we can use them in a variety of ways and for a variety of purposes. [12, pp. 114-122] Language studying must include the teaching and learning of English idioms because they have many advantages for students. Understanding idiomatic expressions improves cultural awareness while also advancing cognitive development, language proficiency, and effective communication. The richness of the English language can be unlocked, students can expand their horizons, and they can improve their communication skills in both academic and practical contexts by im-

mersing themselves in the world of idioms. The importance of learning and teaching English idioms can be attributed to several factors. Overall, during this research, we have come to the conclusion that developing fluency, cultural literacy, and effective communication in the English language require learning English idioms. They definitely help a learner navigate different contexts, give insights into the cultural fabric, and let us interact with people more naturally. We do agree with Levorato, who writes that spontaneous speech becomes difficult without the use of idiomatic language. [11, p.102]

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